

WorkOSH

Workplace Occupational Safety and Health

An Official Newsletter of ENVIS-NIOH

Vol. 17, No. 3
July-Sept. 2022
ISSN: 2393-8943

OCCUPATIONAL CARCINOGENS

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OVERVIEW

Cancer can be caused by substances, or mixtures of substances, called 'carcinogens'. Occupational cancer can be caused through prolonged exposure to carcinogens in the workplace

CARCINOGENESIS

Carcinogenesis or oncogenesis or tumorigenesis is literally the creation of cancer. It is a process by which normal cells are transformed into cancer cells

CAUSES

- Various types exposure of carcinogens
- Tobacco use
- Certain infectious, radiation (persons working with radiation hazards)

- Lack of physical activity
- Poor diet and obesity
- Hereditary: 5-10% of cancers

CLASSIFICATION OF CARCINOGENS

- People are continuously exposed to varying amounts of chemicals that have been shown to have carcinogenic or mutagenic properties in experimental models.
- Chemical carcinogens can occur exogenously or endogenously in living organisms (aerobic metabolic processes, hormonal changes, oxygen uptake and distribution, pathophysiologic states such as inflammation, genetic factors, etc.).
- Exogenous exposure to carcinogens can occur through food consumption, air, occupational exposure and drinking water.
- Exposure to extrinsic or environmental carcinogens may cause 75-80% of human cancers.
- Epidemiological studies suggest that lifestyle causes of cancer such as diet, tobacco smoking, obesity, alcohol, random

sex, etc., are the major contributors to human malignant neoplasms.

Classes of Carcinogens according to International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC)

- On the basis of epidemiological, animal, and in vitro experimental studies, occupational agents linked with cancer have been categorized into 4 major groups by the IARC
 - Group -1 Carcinogenic to humans (21%)
 - Group -2A Probably carcinogenic to humans (16%)
 - Group -2B Possibly carcinogenic to humans (63%)
 - Group -3 Not classifiable
 - Group-4 Not carcinogenic to humans
- **GROUP 1 CARCINOGENS**

40% of IARC group 1 carcinogen are occupational. Others include radiation, viruses and lifestyle factors.

Physical Agents	Associated Cancers
Ionizing radiation	Breast cancer, Leukemia, Skin cancer
UV Rays	Skin cancer

Asbestos	Lung Cancer, Mesothelioma
Chemical Agents	Associated Cancers
Arsenic	Skin cancer, Lung cancer
Vinyl chloride	Liver Angiosarcoma
Aromatic amines	Bladder Cancers

• **GROUP 2A PROBABLE CARCINOGENS**

- ✦ IARC group 2A carcinogens are occupational

Chemical agents	Associated Cancers
Polyaromatic hydrocarbon	Lung, bladder and skin cancers
Wood and fossil fuel products	Skin cancer
Plastic and rubber by products	Bladder cancer
Inorganic lead compounds	Lung cancer
Aromatic amine dyes (e.g. benzidine-based dyes)	Bladder cancer

➤ **GROUP 2B PROBABLE**

CARCINOGENS

- ✦ IARC group 2B carcinogens are occupational.
- ✦ Example: Refractory ceramic fibers, Nickel alloys, Carbon black, Gasoline, Gasoline engine exhaust, Bitumens, Styrene, Acrylonitrile, Chloroform, Dichloromethane, Some Pesticides, Welding fumes.

HIERARCHY OF PREVENTION

MEASURES

- ✦ For carcinogens Workers' exposure must be prevented by implementing measures in a defined order of priority.
- ✦ Elimination is the most effective measure and can be achieved by changing the technology used or the characteristics of the final product, to make the use of carcinogens unnecessary.
- ✦ Substitution means replacing the dangerous substance or product by a safer substance, product process. It should not lead to other hazards with unacceptable levels of risk.

- ✦ If substitution is not technically possible, the employer shall use a closed technological system.
- ✦ If a closed system is not technically possible, the employer shall reduce exposure to a minimum.
- ✦ If there is a risk to workers, specified areas shall only be accessible to workers who, because of their work duties, are required to enter them.
- ✦ If a carcinogen is used, the employer shall:
 - ✦ limit the quantity of the carcinogen;
 - ✦ Keep the number of workers exposed as low as possible.
 - ✦ Design work processes to minimize substance release (i.e. use of collective prevention measures).
 - ✦ Remove carcinogens by extraction ventilation at the source.
 - ✦ Use appropriate procedures to measure carcinogens (especially for early detection of abnormal exposures in the event of unforeseeable events or accidents).
 - ✦ Use individual protection measures if collective protection measures are not sufficient.
- ✦ Mark risk areas clearly and use adequate warning and safety signs.
- ✦ Use sealed and clearly labeled containers for storage, handling, transportation and waste disposal.
- ✦ Exposure shall in no case exceed the occupational exposure limit value of a carcinogen, the employer must ensure proper hygiene (to minimize the risk of contamination). Provisions and conditions must be free of charge for workers and include:
 - ◆ Prohibition of eating, drinking and smoking in areas at risk of contamination;
 - ◆ The provision of appropriate protective clothing and separate storage places for work and non-work clothing;
 - ◆ Access to appropriate washing and toilet facilities;
 - ◆ The availability of appropriate and well-fitting, clean, checked, and maintained protective equipment, stored in a well-defined place. [2]

OCCUPATIONAL EXPOSURE LIMITS (OELS) AND MONITORING

There are OELs in place for several carcinogenic substances. This information should be included in safety data sheets. Compliance with OELs should however be considered the minimum, and efforts should be made to lower exposure as much as possible below these values. The monitoring of carcinogens should be part of a company's carcinogens management strategy and include periodic checks of the efficacy of control measures.

HEALTH SURVEILLANCE

Member States have established arrangements for the health surveillance of workers (prior to exposure, at regular intervals thereafter, and some even after the end of exposure). If a worker is suspected of suffering ill health as a result of exposure, then health surveillance of other exposed workers may be required, and the risk must be reassessed. Individual medical records of concerned workers must be kept. Workers must have access to their personal data and be given information about any health surveillance that they may undergo following the end of the exposure. The workers or the employer may request a review of the results of the health surveillance.

CONCLUSION

- A carcinogen is a substance that is capable of causing, aggravating or promoting cancer in humans or animals. Some carcinogens can be inhaled; others may enter through the skin or mucous membranes. More detailed definitions are

included in the European Directive and national legislation.

- Not every exposure to carcinogens will inevitably lead to cancer: some act following high-level, prolonged exposure, while others act at lower levels and following shorter exposure periods.
- There are a number of carcinogens that workers can be exposed to. Commonly known occupational carcinogens include asbestos, radon, certain pesticides, arsenic and tobacco smoke. Many of the carcinogens to which workers are most frequently exposed are generated by the work processes. Examples include diesel exhaust, welding fumes, crystalline silica dust and hardwood dust. Carcinogens may also be present in raw materials (including impurities), intermediates, products or by-products. The effects of exposure to carcinogens may occur a long time after exposure. Under EU legislation, particularly stringent measures in addition to those required for other dangerous substances must be taken by employers to

prevent harm: eliminating exposure or where this is not possible strict substitution, keeping the carcinogen in a closed system, recording exposures, and stricter information and documentation requirements. Any detailed provisions for the occupational safety and health (OSH) management of carcinogens are laid down in national regulations.

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Some Carcinogens in the Work Place

Carcinogen	Occupation	Type of Cancer
Arsenic	Mining, pesticide workers	Lung, skin, liver
Asbestos	Construction workers	Lung, mesothelioma
Benzene	Petroleum, rubber, chemical workers	Leukemia
Chromium	Metal workers, electroplaters	Lung
Leather dust	Shoe manufacturing	Nasal, bladder
Naphthylamine	Chemical, dye, rubber workers	Bladder
Radon	Underground mining	Lung
Soots, tars, oils	Coal, gas, petroleum workers	Lung, skin, liver
Vinyl chloride	Rubber workers, polyvinyl chloride manufacturing	Liver
Wood dust	Furniture manufacturing	Nasal

Artwork by Jeanne Kelly, © 2004

Image Source: https://cisncancer.org/cancer101/what_causes_cancer_06.html

IARC Classifications

GROUP	WHAT IT MEANS	EXAMPLES
<p>Group 1</p> <p>Carcinogenic to Humans</p>	<p>There is sufficient evidence the agent causes cancer in humans.</p>	<p>Solar radiation, processed meats, alcoholic beverages, smoking, asbestos, talc-based baby powder contaminated with asbestos</p>
<p>Group 2A</p> <p>Probably Carcinogenic to Humans</p>	<p>There is sufficient evidence the agent causes cancer in humans.</p>	<p>Anabolic steroids, high temperature frying, HPV, red meat, Roundup (glyphosate), Actos (pioglitazone), N-nitrosodiethylamine (NDMA)</p>
<p>Group 2B</p> <p>Possibly Carcinogenic to Humans</p>	<p>Limited evidence in humans and less than sufficient evidence in animals.</p>	<p>Aloe vera leaf extract, marine diesel fuel, gasoline, engine exhaust, Asian pickled vegetables, progestin, perineal use of talc-based body powder</p>
<p>Group 3</p> <p>Not Classifiable as to its Carcinogenicity in Humans</p>	<p>Evidence is inadequate in humans and inadequate or limited in animals.</p>	<p>Coffee, low-frequency electric fields, dental materials, ceramic implants, chlorinated drinking water, tea, printing inks</p>

Image Source: <https://www.drugwatch.com/health/cancer/carcinogens>

Published by: **ENVIS Resource Partner**
ICMR - National Institute of Occupational Health,
 Meghaninagar, Ahmedabad-380016.